

COST, RETURNS AND PROFITABILITY OF COTTON CULTIVATION IN NANDED DISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

The present study was designed to calculate cost and returns in Nanded district has been purposively selected for the study because Mukhed and Kandhar tehsils having highest area under cotton crop as compared to other tehsils in the Nanded district. 15 kharif Cotton growers were randomly selected from each selected villages. Thus from 6 villages, 90 growers were selected. The results revealed that per hectare labour requirement of cotton were 36.33 man days in case of hired human labour and 17.43 man days in case of family human labour on cotton farm i.e. in total 53.76 man days human labour were utilized for cotton crop. The use of hired labour is utilized maximum on farm. On the farms 0.97 pair days of bullock labour were utilized per hectare. Cost-A was ₹ 62954.0 and Cost-B was ₹ 89082.49, for a total cost per hectare of ₹ 105659.94, output input ratio (B: C Ratio) was 1.62, showing net profit was earned in cotton crop 60572.28 and yield of cotton main produce 22.31 q/ha.

Key words: Cotton, Cost, Returns, Profitability**Introduction**

Cotton, scientifically known as *Gossypium hirsutum* for upland cotton, is the most widely cultivated species. Other species include *Gossypium barbadense* (Pima cotton) and *Gossypium herbaceum* (Levant cotton). Upland cotton has a chromosome number of $2n=52$. Grown primarily for its fiber, cotton is essential for clothing production. It also provides oil from seeds, with oil content ranging from 15-20 per cent, higher in American cotton. After oil extraction, the cottonseed cake is valuable as organic manure and cattle feed. Cotton plays a crucial role in human civilization, dubbed the "king of apparel fiber" and "white gold of India" due to its significance. India ranks first in cotton acreage, with 120.69 lakh hectares under cultivation (36% of the world total). Cotton is grown on various soils, from sandy loam to black soils, with adaptability based on species and rainfall conditions. India's cotton production primarily occurs in the Northern, Central, and Southern zones.

India leads global cotton production with 362.18 lakh bales (2021-22), contributing 23 per cent of the world total. It is also the second-largest consumer, accounting for 22 per cent of global consumption, and the third-largest exporter. Despite being a leading producer, India imports a small percentage of cotton to meet specific industry requirements.

Objective

Per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton production

Materials And Method

For the 2022-23 study year, survey method of data collection was used for collection of data from the selected area. The Nanded district has been purposively selected for the study used to select two tehsils, Mukhed and Kandhar, known for high cotton production and fertilizer consumption. From the each tehsil, three villages were selected on the basis of highest area under of cotton crop production. The villages viz., Himpalnari, Akhargha and Kabnur from Mukhed tehsil, villages viz., Digras, Mundewadi and Guntur from Kandhar tehsil and Fifteen cultivators from each village were selected. 15 kharif Cotton growers were randomly selected from each selected villages. Thus from 6 villages, 90 growers were selected. Farmers were interviewed personally at their farm and residence.

Statistical tools applied: Frequency, Percentage, and Average**Results And Discussion****Physical inputs and outputs in cotton production.**

Per hectare physical inputs and outputs of cotton production were calculated and presented in Table 1. The primary inputs include hired human labour, both male and female, which amounted to 87.23 man-days. Bullock labour was minimal, with only 0.93 pair-days used, representing. Machine labour contributed slightly more with 1.73

hours. The use of seeds was relatively low at 2.22 kg per hectare. Manures played a significant role in cotton production, with 4.58 tons used per hectare. Fertilizers were also heavily relied upon, with nitrogen (N) used at 75.75 kg/ha, phosphorus (P) at 53.93 kg/ha, and potassium (K) at 41 kg/ha. In terms of plant protection, 0.5 liters of Profex Super, 150 grams of Ulalla, and 1 kg of Acephate were applied. Irrigation charges were found to be 2.44 per cent, ensuring adequate water supply for the crop. On the output side, the main produce amounted to 22.31 quintals per hectare, complemented by 7 quintals of by-produce.

Per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton production

Per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton were calculated and presented in Table 2. The total cost of cultivation is categorized into different heads, which include labour, input costs, interest, and depreciation. Hired human labour accounts for the largest share of the total cost, with an expenditure of ₹34,892 per hectare, representing 36.33 per cent of the total cost. This reflects the labour-intensive nature of cotton production. Hired bullock and machine labour contribute smaller portions, with bullock labour accounting for 0.97 per cent and machine labour contributing 1.80 per cent, respectively. Seed and manure costs are also important components. The value of seed, calculated at ₹1,450 per kilogram, leads to a total of ₹3,219 (3.35 per cent of total cost), while the value of manure accounts for ₹4,580, constituting 4.77 per cent of the total cost. Regarding fertilizers, the main components used are Nitrogen (N), Phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K). Nitrogen, applied at 75.75 kg per hectare, incurs a cost of ₹5,326.74 (5.55 per cent of total cost), while Phosphorus and Potassium are applied at 53.93 kg and 41 kg, costing ₹1,922.90 (2.00 per cent) and ₹2,325.52 (2.42 per cent), respectively. In plant protection measures, specific chemicals like Profex Super, Ulalla and Acephate are used, with their combined cost accounting for 2.96 per cent of the total cost. The most notable expense among these is Ulalla, with a cost of ₹1,500, representing 1.56 per cent. The table also considers the interest on working capital at 6 per cent, which adds ₹1,826.42 to the total cost, contributing 1.90 per cent of the overall cost. Depreciation on fixed assets is minimal, at ₹203.39 (0.21 per cent). When breaking down the total cost into various levels, Cost A1, which includes all paid-out costs, is ₹62,954.00, making up 65.54 per cent of the total cost.

The inclusion of revenue value of land adds ₹26,128.49, bringing Cost A2 to the same as A1. When considering interest on fixed capital at 10 per cent, the cost rises slightly to ₹64,353.40 (67.00 per cent of the total). The total cost, including family labour and other imputed costs, is ₹96,054.49, representing the complete economic cost of production. Additionally, adding the imputed managerial cost (Cost C3) brings the

overall expense to ₹1,05,659.94. This detailed cost structure helps to understand the various components involved in cotton cultivation, allowing for a more comprehensive assessment of the economic viability of cotton production under specific conditions.

Profitability of cotton production

Per hectare profitability in cotton production was calculated and presented in Table 4.6. The profitability of cotton production per hectare reveals several key insights. The total gross returns from cotton production, which includes both the main produce and the by-produce, amount to ₹156,814.32. From this, the returns from the main produce are significantly higher at ₹153,314.32, while the by-produce contributes ₹3,500. On examining the costs, the cost of production follows a structured categorization. The lowest cost category, Cost A1, stands at ₹62,954.01, while the highest, Cost C3, amounts to ₹105,866.24. Each of these cost categories represents various levels of inputs, with Cost C3 including imputed family labour and managerial costs. The per quintal cost of production is calculated to be ₹4,588.35, and the net income generated from cotton production is ₹90,572.28. This indicates a healthy return to the farmer, reflecting the economic viability of the crop. Notably, the returns over variable costs (RVC) are ₹93,890.31, showing that after covering variable expenses, a significant portion of revenue remains.

Farm Business Income (FBI), which is the income over and above paid-out costs, is ₹155,414.93, while the Family Labour Income (FLI), which considers the imputed value of family labour, is ₹67,731.82. The return to management, which accounts for the managerial costs, stands at ₹50,948.07. Finally, the output to input ratio is 1.62, signifying that for every rupee invested in cotton production, there is a return of ₹1.62. This ratio highlights the profitability of cotton production, suggesting that it is a rewarding venture for farmers when managed efficiently.

Conclusion

The present investigation was intended to depict the picture of the

cotton growing enterprises in Nanded district. The results revealed that, per hectare gross return was found to be ₹ 156814.32 in cotton farm. It was clear that, farm business income, family labour income and net profit/ha were ₹ 155414.93 ₹ 67731.82 and ₹ 60572.28, respectively. It was clear that, output-input ratio was 1.62. It implied that, when 1 rupee spent on cotton production, it would lead to give the returns of ₹ 1.62. Per quintal cost of production of cotton was ₹4588.35.

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Table 1: Per hectare use of physical input and output in cotton production (Unit/ha)

Sr. no.	Particulars	Unit	Quantity
	Input		
1	Hired human labour (Male + Female)	man days	87.23
2	Bullock labour	pair days	0.93
3	Machine labour	hrs	1.73
4	Seed	kg	2.22
5	Manures	ton	4.58
6	Fertilizer		
	N	kg	75.75
	P	kg	53.93
	K	kg	41
7	Plant protection		
	Profex super	l	0.5
	Ulalla	gm	150
	Acephate	kg	1
8	Irrigation Charge		
	Output		
9	Main produce	qt	22.31
10	By produce	qt	7

Table 2: Per hectare cost of cultivation of cotton production

No	Cost Items	Unit	Quantity	Rate (₹)	Amount (₹)	Percentage
1	Hired Human Labour	Man days	87.23	400	34892	36.33
2	Hired bullock	Pair days	0.93	1000	930	0.97
3	Hired machine	hrs	1.73	1000	1730	1.80
4	Seed	kg	2.22	1450	3219	3.35
5	Manure	ton	4.58	1000	4580	4.77
6	Fertilizer					0.00
	Nitrogen (N)	kg	75.75	70.32	5326.74	5.55

Table 3: Per hectare profitability of cotton production (₹/ha)

Sr. No.	Particulars	Amount (₹)				
1	Returns from a main produce					153314.32
2	Returns from a by produce					3500
	Gross returns (1+2)					156814.32
3	Cost – A ₁					62954.01
4	Cost – A ₂					62954.01
5	Cost – B ₁					64353.39
6	Cost – B ₂					89082.49
7	Cost – C ₁					71512.94
8	Cost – C ₂					96242.03
9	Cost – C ₃					105866.24
10	Per quintal cost of production					4588.35
11	Returns over variable cost (RVC)					93890.31
12	Farm Business income (FBI)					155414.93
13	Family labour income (FLI)					67731.82
14	Net Income					60572.28
15	Return to management					50948.07
16	Output to input ratio					1.62
	Phosphorus (P)	kg	53.93	35.65	1922.90	2.00
	Potassium (K)	kg	41.00	56.72	2325.52	2.42
7	Plant protection					0.00
	Profex super	Litre	0.5	700	350	0.36
	Ulalla	gm	150	10	1500	1.56
	Acephate	kg	1	1000	1000	1.04
11	Interest Working Capital @ 6%				1826.42	1.90
12	Land Revenue				43.41	0.05
13	Depreciation				203.39	0.21
	Cost A1				62954.00	65.54
	Rental value of land				26128.48	27.20
	Cost A2				62954.00	65.54
14	Interest Fixed Capital @ 10%				1399.39	1.46
	Cost B1				64353.39	67.00
	Cost B2				89082.49	92.74
16	Family Labour	Man days	17.43	400	6972	7.26
	Cost C1				71325.39	74.26
	Cost C2				99054.49	100.00
	Cost C3				105659.94	